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EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF DEFENCE AND NATIONAL SECURITY PROJECTS BASED ON PRINCE2 METHODOLOGY ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE POLICE ACADEMY IN SZCZYTNO

The article presents issues related to the preparation and implementation of projects involving Polish and European aid funds. The author emphasises that the implementation of each project is a complex undertaking, requiring timely and effective and effective action in accordance with the assumed objectives and, above all, the adopted parameters. Effective project management requires specific competences possessed by the implementation team appointed for this purpose, as well as specific skills of this team. The article presents the characteristics of project management, stages of project implementation, the PRINCE2 project management methodology in the Police and the implementation of projects at the Police Academy in Szczytno using the PRINCE2 methodology, taking into account the structure of the project management team. The author believes that project failure is often due to poor project management, the lack of use of an appropriate management methodology. How a project is managed largely determines its success. Proper project management is one of the elements of success, not only of the project itself, but also of the success of the applicant and the entities to which the support, whether in-kind or financial, has been directed.

Keywords: project management, project team, public administration, project manager, PRINCE2 methodology.

MANAGEMENTUL EFICIENT AL PROIECTELOR DE APĂRARE ȘI SECURITATE NAȚIONALĂ PE BAZA METODOLOGIEI PRINCE2 PE EXEMPLUL ACADEMIEI DE POLIȚIE DIN SZCZYTNO

În articolul sunt prezentate probleme legate de pregătirea și implementarea proiectelor care implică fonduri de ajutor poloneze și europene. Autorul subliniază că implementarea fiecărui proiect este un angajament complex, care necesită o acțiune în timp util și eficientă în concordanță cu obiectivele asumate și, mai ales, cu parametrii adoptați. Managementul eficient al proiectului

necesită competențe specifice deținute de echipa de implementare desemnată în acest scop, precum și competențe specifice acestei echipe. Articolul prezintă caracteristicile managementului de proiect, etapele implementării proiectului, metodologia de management de proiect PRINCE2 în Poliție și implementarea proiectelor la Academia de Poliție din Szczytno cu folosirea metodologiei PRINCE2, ținând cont de structura echipei de management al proiectului. Autorul consideră că eșecul proiectului se datorează adesea managementului defectuos al acestuia, lipsei utilizării unei metodologii de management adecvate. Modul în care este gestionat un proiect determină în mare măsură succesul acestuia. Managementul corect al proiectului este unul dintre elementele succesului, nu numai al proiectului în sine, ci și al succesului solicitantului și al entităților cărora le-a fost îndreptat sprijinul, în natură sau financiar.

Cuvinte-cheie: management de proiect, echipă de proiect, administrație publică, manager de proiect, metodologia PRINCE2.

1. INTRODUCTION.

In today's rapidly changing environment, the success of an organisation depends largely on self-improvement, i.e. how to prepare for and implement changes performed under time and cost pressure. The execution of tasks largely determined by time and financial resources is the domain of undertakings called projects. The term project functions in our consciousness in very many meanings. The answer to the question 'what is a project' asked in different communities will result in a different answer. An engineer, an artist, a financier, a lawyer or a person with a humanistic background will think differently about a project. However, project management methodologies need to define the concept of a project in a very precise way. According to the PRINCE2 methodology, a project is 'A management environment designed to deliver one or more business products according to the specific requirements of the business'¹. The most important element of a project – the business need – follows directly from this definition. This business need will form the basis for one of the first management documents – the project business case which forms the basis for further project planning and execution.

This article will present one of the of project management methods – PRINCE2 methodology as an effective methodology for managing defence and national security pro-

jects used for many years at the Police Academy in Szczytno.

2. METHODOLOGY.

The methodology of document analysis, the literature on the subject and the legal acts in force at the Police Academy in Szczytno were used during the research.

3. RESULTS.

3.1. Project preparation and implementation. Project management

Preparing and implementing a project with the aid of both national and European funds is a complex undertaking, requiring timely and effective action in accordance with the assumed objectives and, above all, the adopted parameters. Effective project management requires specific competencies possessed by the implementation team appointed for this purpose, as well as specific skills of this team. Broadly understood competencies consist of qualifications, experience and personality traits. The European Union, including Poland, does not impose on project developers a single method of developing and managing projects. Nevertheless, projects developed in accordance with accepted project management standards, such as PRINCE2 or PMBOK® Guide, are evaluated more highly. As a rule, the proposed project management methodologies are supposed to eliminate negative phenomena and excessive risk of implemented projects regardless of their nature and area of implementation. The most important negative phenomena commonly occurring in programmes or projects

¹ 'A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge Third Edition' (PMBOK® Guide), Project Management Institute.

include: poor planning and preparation of projects, as well as their inadequacy to meet the needs of final beneficiaries. Therefore, the preparation of appropriate methodological solutions is important from the point of view of participants in any project. These solutions concern the achievement of project objectives within a defined financial limit, and their correct implementation and evaluation increases the likelihood that the funds received will be spent purposefully. When we talk about management principles, we often mean managing people. In turn, managing people involves defining the activities of organisational units, planning tasks for individuals, organising work, monitoring the performance of tasks and, finally, evaluating. The same applies to project management. According to R. K. Wysocki, 'Project management is a set of methods and techniques based on accepted management principles used to plan, evaluate and control the activities of desired results – on time and on budget, and in accordance with the requirements'².

Project management is also defined as planning, organising, monitoring and directing all aspects of a project and motivating all project participants, leading to the confident achievement of project objectives, safely and within agreed time, cost and performance criteria.

Project management, according to A. Zajączkowska, is also defined as 'the application of knowledge, skills, tools and methods and the harmonisation of the interaction of project implementers to achieve the set objectives, to complete projects within the set time period and to keep costs within the set limit. The management process makes it possible to steer the course of a project. It is the undertaking of integrated activities to achieve project objectives' [14, p. 27].

The American Project Management Institute's definition is that 'project management is the management discipline concerned with applying available knowledge, skills, tools and techniques to meet the needs and expectations of project principals' [2, p. 27]. There are interrelationships between the project management terms presented, as project management as a field of knowledge creates a source of knowledge for managing projects in specific situations. The following, in tabular form, is a specification of project management by E. Turban and J.R. Meredith, which defines the typical characteristics of projects, the main features of project management and the symptoms of mismanagement of projects.

Management is an indispensable part of any project and one of the most impor-

Table 1. Characteristics of project management

Project characteristics	Characteristics of project management	Symptoms of inadequate project management
Uniqueness	Uncertainty	Cost overruns
Longevity	Unpredictability	Deviation from plan
Complexity	Difficulties of implementation	Non-compliance with technical requirements
Significant participation of external contractors	Dependence on external partners	Problems with enforcing contracts
Intensive cooperation	Difficulties in planning	Communication disruption
Multilateral relationships	Need for visualisation	Coordination difficulties
High risk	Special control by the top management	Criticism from the general public, reluctance to take bold decisions
High potential benefits	Of special interest to the top management	Attacks from competitors

Źródło: E. Turban, J.R. Meredith, *Fundamentals of Management Science, Business Publications, Plano 1985, p. 320.*

² *Ibid.*, p. 62.

tant criteria of its assessment. According to the provisions of the application generator for PO KL, it includes the following stages:

- 1) start of the project,
- 2) implementation of project activities,
- 3) project evaluation,
- 4) project closing [2, p. 28].

Project management taking into account the above-mentioned stages is illustrated in the figure below.

Project management according to the project life cycle includes consecutive phases such as identification, planning, implementation and evaluation. The final evaluation of a project can take the form of an audit.

There are at least 30 different project management methodologies worldwide. In Poland, the most common project manage-

PRINCE2 (a clear and elaborate hierarchy of decision-making levels, where the project coordinator is responsible for the day-to-day management of activities during each phase of the project. The methodology defines a project as an organisation set up for a period of time to deliver one or more business products, according to a defined business case. It leads to a focus on the business aspects of the project, starting with the reasons for bringing the project to life and ending it with its closure [1, p. 21-26]), **IPMA** (an organisation registered in Switzerland that has created an international standard ICB – competence guidelines, according to which a project coordinator should possess not only knowledge and experience, but also high interpersonal skills, which are essential to carry out projects

Chart 1. Project management

Source: A. Zajączkowska, *Project coordinator ...* p. 28.

ment standards include: **PMBOK®Guide** (used mostly in commercial organisations, giving a very high degree of autonomy to the coordinator in project management),

successfully. He treats project management as an independent profession), **PCM** methodology – Project Cycle Management, based on the Logic Table Analysis method, which is

the main tool used for project planning during the project identification and development phase. The experience to date in project management in Poland, is largely based on the PCM methodology, which is recommended by the European Commission. The use of this methodology in project management is often referred to as an 'integrated approach' to project lifecycle management, as it aims to support good management practice and effective decision-making during the project lifecycle. Using common project management standards results in the project commissioner, the project manager and those working on the project having a clear understanding of what work should be organised and how the project has been planned and should be implemented [7, p. 5].

When preparing an application (application for funding for a project), project developers usually have one goal in mind – to obtain funding. Many issues are postponed, while every poorly thought-out sentence in the project can generate unnecessary problems at the very beginning of the project. In addition to careful planning of the project's scope of activities, it is necessary to create a management structure that can cope with the considerable number of requirements at the implementation stage. Therefore, when embarking on project management, it is important to familiarise yourself with the various project management standards and select the most appropriate management methodology for your project.

3.2. Project management methodology PRINCE2 in Police

In the management of projects whose beneficiary is the Police, from my own experience, I can state that the PRINCE2 methodology is becoming more and more widespread (increasingly used in the management of research projects and development work for national security and defence at the Police Academy in Szczytno and for ICT projects at the Police Headquarters in Warsaw). The PRINCE2 methodology is widely used in more than 150 countries around the world and demand for it is growing steadily. It is

widely regarded as the leading project management methodology, as evidenced by the more than 20,000 organisations already benefiting from this approach. Today, complex projects often involve several organisations working in partnership or under contract to achieve their objectives. The PRINCE 2 methodology provides a common language when dealing with different organisations and with external suppliers [6]. In addition, it is so generic that it can be applied to any project regardless of the scale and type of project, organisation, geographical location or culture. Because the methodology is generic and based on proven principles, organisations adopting this methodology as a standard can significantly improve their organisational capability and maturity in many spheres, such as research, development of the manufactured product, IT, etc. More on this methodology later in this paper.

Returning to the consideration of project management, it should be noted that it is undoubtedly the art of dealing with unexpected events and counteracting or minimising their harmful consequences. One of the most important conditions for the success of a project is involving the right people and using the right tools. Project management has become an intrinsic part of making a difference in the life of an organisation, and the smooth execution of projects contributes to its success.

Based on my own long experience in project management, I have to say that project management does not end when the grant is paid into the beneficiary's account. It is necessary to remember about the sustainability of a project, also after its completion. This element is related to the maintenance of the effects achieved as a result of the project within 5 years from its completion. Achieving the success of receiving a grant requires hard work, but above all, punctuality. Therefore, every applicant should be aware of the effectiveness and essence of project management.

Project management issues are not the simplest. It should be remembered that project management is much broader than writing an application. It is the implementation of the en-

tire project that is assessed, not just the submitted application. The correct implementation of a project does not only depend on practical skills, but equally importantly on constant deepening of theoretical knowledge [10, p. 9].

The basis for implementing projects co-financed by national or foreign funds is, of course, money. However, it would be a great simplification to look at the implementation of the application from this angle only. Receiving a grant entails great responsibility on the part of the applicant, not only in terms of proper project management, but also proper spending of the granted funds for the implementation of the project, be it a training (soft) or investment (hard) project, achieving the assumed project objectives and indicators. Expenditure of funds must be carried out in accordance with their purpose, with the applicable legal regulations on eligibility and expenditure of funds under a given programme.

In accordance with the Community regulations currently in force, the principle is, inter alia, to finance EU projects from the resources of only one fund (mono-fund principle). In order to avoid many problems in project management, it is worth taking the time to learn about project management methodologies and to consider the time needed to prepare a good project [3].

According to Stanisław Sroka, President of the Management Board of the Project Management Association Poland, project management skills cannot bypass public administration. He claims that 'in times of dynamic changes, globalisation, EU-funded projects, both business and authorities will not do without professional management methods, as projects will soon become an everyday occurrence.' [5].

Public administration, and therefore also the police, is faced with the task of preparing its staff for skilful project management, and this is the case for the majority of its staff involved in obtaining and using aid funds. Effective project management is, above all, the cooperation of a team of people dealing with various areas within an institution.

In the most developed countries, pro-

fessional project management is already a common phenomenon. In Poland, it is only just beginning to be applied, mainly in industries where the tasks to be performed are of a project nature. The guiding principle is 'do it on time and for the money'.

In many countries around the world, project management has become so crucial that without a professionally prepared and certified team, a task has no chance of being funded from other sources, such as public money, or of being implemented. Project management has also become common, if not fashionable, in the police force.

The modern Police poses new challenges to the management, requiring constant improvement of their competences, also in the area of obtaining aid funds. Problems related to the planning and implementation of projects co-financed from EU funds in many police organisational units are not a new issue. Since the 1990s, the Polish Police has been an active beneficiary of aid funds, in particular European funds. This state of affairs required, and still requires, specific standards for project management within the existing organisational structures in the Police, which will enable efficient and more effective implementation of projects, both national and European.

What does national project management or EU project management include?

The following management areas can be distinguished in the management of any project, which can also be distinguished in projects managed by police units, i.e:

- human resources management (e.g. consortium formation, communication between partners, division of roles in the project, organisation of meetings, decision-making, how to resolve disputes and conflicts, and others);

- material resources management (e.g. choosing the project site, equipment, planning the purchase of equipment, materials necessary for the project)

- financial management (e.g. setting the project budget, allocation of funds for the realisation of individual tasks, salary planning, expenses, valuation of own contribu-

tion, watching over the flow of funds),

– time management (duration of the project, time allocation of tasks, when the main and specific objectives of the project are to be achieved, when reports are to be written, when meetings and audits are to be scheduled, when funds are to be transferred by the coordinator

– intellectual property rights management (who will own possible patents, who will be allowed to disseminate the results of the research and in what form, at what point confidentiality will have to be maintained, etc.).

Police practice in project management indicates that simply isolating projects in the planning system and linking them to costs and outputs does not ensure the expected efficiency of activities. This situation can, among other things, lead to a loss of proper control over projects, which prevents the achievement of the intended objectives and results of projects. It has therefore become necessary to create a mechanism for coordinating the course of the project from planning to completion, i.e. project management.

In order to achieve this, in many police units internal regulations have been introduced in the form of orders of commanders, decisions, regulations, as well as, in the case of the Police Academy in Szczytno, in the form of the aforementioned acts, but also Senate Resolutions, which speak about the implementation of projects, both investment projects and various training undertakings with the use of external funds, employment and remuneration of persons within the projects, creation of project teams and other.

Successful project management is not determined by the number of people involved in project activities, but by the way the work is organised. The existing linear organisational structures of many police units and the complexity of project issues involving several entities within a given structure did not allow the application of a simple linear project management system. Therefore, it was necessary to decide on the creation of project teams for the implementation of specific projects from the existing employees of the organisation, which

conditioned the project management structure. At present, there are appropriate teams in each police unit (provincial police headquarters), dealing, among other things, with the acquisition of aid funds for the Police.

In management theory, project teams are referred to variously and appear as project management offices, programme and project offices, project management centres, project support offices and others. Many definitions of a project team can be found in the literature. According to Jerzy Rosiński, a project team is an 'organisational unit, established on the basis of subject specialisation, realising a project under direct supervision of a project manager' [8, p. 196]. G. Kendall i S. Rollins definition of the project team as a centralised organisation dedicated to improving project management practices and results³. The success of the project depends on the staff in the project team. Teams are set up to carry out a project task and are disbanded upon completion.

Analysing the potential possibilities for the implementation of projects from external sources by police units, the following entities can be singled out, whose participation becomes advisable and even necessary for the proper implementation of the project. These are: Department/Section of Finance, Department/Section of Public Procurement, Team of Legal Advisors, the relevant substantive department of a given unit in relation to the scope of the project (e.g. Department of Information Technology for IT projects, Department/Section of Investment and Repairs for investment projects, Prevention Department for projects concerning prevention programmes, training in crime prevention, traffic, crisis management, Criminal Department for projects concerning economic crime, human trafficking and others, Press Team, Internal Auditor, etc.). Within the scope of the activities of police units, we can distinguish two types of projects, which include: 'soft' projects, concerning training projects, international cooperation, implemented in partnership with other entities, and 'hard' projects – investment projects in the area

³ <http://pl.wikipedia.org>.

of IT, communications, transport, supplies, investments and renovations. Successes and failures in project implementation are determined by a variety of factors. According to J. Kisielnicki, the organisation of the project team, i.e. the organisation of the executive level cells, has a huge impact on the success of a project [4].

Regardless of the selected area, activities undertaken in projects, the size and composition of the project team will depend on many factors, including, but not limited to, the type of project (training, investment), the formula for project implementation (project implemented in partnership or as an independent project), the size of the project in the context of the project budget and its area of influence (e.g. the entire Poland, region, police unit). For independent projects, apart from the project manager and coordinator or operational manager (in the case of projects managed in accordance with the PRINCE2 methodology), the project team may also include managers of police organisational units which are competent in terms of the scope and place of project realisation, e.g. Director of the Office of the Cabinet of the KGP, Head of the Finance Department, Head of the Prevention Department, Director of the Institute of Law and others. Each of these managers, depending on the needs, may appoint 1-2 persons who, at the level of implementation of the unit's tasks, will be responsible for them.

The number of participants in project teams, depending on the specifics of the project, its scope and the structure of the unit, can vary from 5-25 people. However, it is important to bear in mind that project team members need to be mutually responsible for the implementation of the project, to take action and achieve goals together, to engage in the work together, to complement each other's skills. Project team members should recognise the need for each other's experience in order to achieve common goals. Communication within the project team is also important and should always be characterised by honesty and trust. The primary reason for setting up project teams is the timing of the project.

In the literature, there are many tips on how to proceed in order to create a good project team that will provide the best conditions for the success of the project. Undoubtedly, the allocation of responsibility to the different functions performed in the project is of great importance.

A good solution in the Police turned out to be the creation in individual police units, mainly at the level of provincial police headquarters, police schools, the KSP, the KGP and the Police Academy in Szczytno of basic organisational units, sometimes independent, subordinate to a large extent directly to the provincial police chiefs, school commanders or the commander-rector of the Police Academy in Szczytno, teams/departments dealing with the acquisition of aid funds, sometimes also with public procurement, which guarantees much higher effectiveness of work in this respect.

The other subjects – the project participants – fall under different management divisions, so issues of leadership and coordination of project activities are important. From the point of view of effective project management, cooperation between the project team leader and its members is important, where the leader will have an overriding role in relation to the team members. In this way, he or she will be able to exert enough influence on them to enable them to carry out their tasks efficiently.

In projects, the positions of coordinator, specialists and assistants have become accepted, but this is not a mandatory set. The most important thing is that the distribution of tasks.

The most important thing is that the distribution of tasks and dependencies between the various positions in a project is clear and guarantees effective management.

The wide range of core tasks performed by the project manager and the new subject matter associated with the implementation of various projects points to a solution that involves appointing a project coordinator or operational project manager in addition to the project manager. This coordinator or operational manager often comes from the

organisational unit dealing with fundraising in the police unit and is primarily responsible for administrative and content-related support of the project, including communication support within the project team and communication with external institutions involved in project implementation, e.g. partners, institutions implementing projects, supervising project implementation and others. In addition, persons working in the appointed teams for assistance funds in police units perform coordinating functions for all projects implemented within a given police voivodeship headquarters, police school, the Police Headquarters or the Police Academy in Szczytno. Depending on the selected project manager, the coordinator functions in double or triple subordination for the duration of the project, depending on the number and type of projects implemented, which sometimes causes difficulties in proper project implementation.

Usually, projects in the police are traditionally managed on the basis of internal regulations, created for the purpose of project implementation, where the persons included in project teams, their tasks, responsibility, subordination, methods of communication, making key decisions, etc. are designated. However, nowadays, there is an increasing emphasis by various institutions, launching competitions, on managing projects based on an accepted, arbitrary project management methodology, e.g. PRINCE2, PMBOK, or another one mentioned earlier.

These methodologies can be a valuable source of solutions and guidance which, once the specifics of the institution that is the Police are taken into account, can provide important support for building a management concept for a specific project of a specific police unit. Therefore, in Police units, e.g. the Police Academy in Szczytno, the Central Forensic Police Laboratory in Warsaw, projects are increasingly being managed based on the PRINCE2 methodology. Additionally, for this element, described in the application form (point concerning project management) with an indication of the selected project management methodology, the beneficiary

may receive, during the evaluation, additional points. For this reason, some police units, including APol, educate their employees in the selected project management methodology, directing them to training courses organised by external companies.

3.3. Project implementation at the Police Academy in Szczytno using the PRINCE2 methodology

In projects implemented at the Police Academy in Szczytno in the field of defence and national security, funded by the National Centre for Research and Development, a Project Management Team is established using the PRINCE2 methodology. The Steering Committee (SC), consisting of representatives of the leader (Police Academy in Szczytno), consortium partners and possibly potential end-users of the project, is responsible for making strategic decisions in the project. The overarching role in the Steering Committee is held by the Chair of the Steering Committee, who has ultimate responsibility for the project. The other members are an advisory body. The Chair of the Steering Committee requests the appointment of Steering Committee members on the side of the Main Supplier (consortium partners), who design, produce, support, supply and implement the project products, and the Main User (leader, potential recipients of the project end results), who is responsible for determining the needs of those who will use the project products. The Steering Committee is accountable to the University's management for the successful implementation of the project and has strategic project management responsibilities. In addition, it is responsible for communication between the project management team and stakeholders outside the project management team. The Steering Committee disposes of the funds provided for the project and oversees the implementation of the project and the proper spending of the funds.

In particular, the SC's tasks include:

- approving plans for the implementation of individual stages of the project schedule
- approving the final results of the im-

plementation of the research and development stages of the project and giving permission to start the next stage in the project;

- managing project risks and making key decisions

- regarding the introduction of emergency plans;

- issuing general guidelines for project implementation;

- approving changes to the project scope, schedule and cost estimate;

- making decisions on issues submitted to the Steering Committee;

- supervising the proper implementation of the project in terms of its legitimacy

and further continuation of the project, realisation of the main objective and detailed objectives of the project, project schedule and cost estimate;

- approval of interim reports on the implementation of the Project milestones and the final report;

- approval of the project closure;

- delegating authority and issuing guidance to management team members;

- improving communication processes between members of the Project Management Team and the unit's management, and responding to the needs communicated by the main recipients and users of the project.

The Chair of the Steering Committee is approved by the Commandant-Rector already at the application preparation stage. He/she has the ultimate responsibility for the project, being supported by the Lead User and the Lead Supplier. The role of the Chairperson is to ensure that the project remains focused throughout its lifecycle on the achievement of its objectives and on the delivery of a product that will deliver the anticipated benefits. The Chairman must also ensure that the project creates value for money by delivering the project in a cost-conscious manner that balances the requirements of the business, user and supplier. Throughout the life of the project, the Chairman is responsible for the business case (the justification for the project, including costs, benefits, risks, timescales, against which its continued valid-

ity is verified). In addition, the Chairman also makes the final decisions and is supported by the Lead User and Lead Supplier in making these decisions.

Project management cannot be completed without a good project manager. This role is played by a project manager who should possess a number of competencies and skills that will enable him or her to carry out a project in accordance with the principal's requirements and, in so doing, not to exceed the deadline and the approved budget. The person who is appointed to this position is responsible for the implementation of the project and the end result of the project, which is formally reflected in the project initiation documentation. As a rule, only one project manager is appointed for a given project team. For the duration of a project, a project manager should not be in charge of multiple projects at the same time. The requirements for the manager depend on the specifics of the project and the members of the Project Team.

The Project Manager coordinates the work of the Project Team, which is made up of persons responsible for the actual execution of activities, actions within the assigned tasks of the project schedule, and the achievement of final results of a specified range and quality parameters. The role of the project manager is managerial in nature, however, in addition to mastering the basic managerial roles, project management requires this person to be above average in simultaneously performing many different functions in the project environment. The project manager identifies a project operations manager who supports the Chair of the Steering Committee in all management activities of the project.

A project operational manager is a person who supports the project manager in the day-to-day coordination of the project in accordance with the established schedule, cost estimate, substantive scope and objectives of the project, established indicators for the project. Within the Project Management Team there is also a separate structure of a nature supporting the Project Manager in the scope of project management, the so-called Project

Support. Persons involved in project support are paid from the project's indirect costs. The Project Support team includes persons responsible for administrative, financial and legal support of the entire project, a person responsible for public procurement, members of organisational units responsible within the unit for procurement and warehouse management. In addition, individual units are required to provide assistance. Project support is not mandatory from a formal point of view. If it is not, the Project Manager can fulfil this role. The Project Support function can also be carried out by the Project Office or by persons specifically designated for the project.

The structure of the project management team based on the PRINCE2 methodology is shown in the chart below.

At the Police Academy in Szczytno, a number of nationally funded defence and national security development projects are managed based on the PRINCE2 methodology. However, it should be emphasised that the people who manage these projects, in the unit responsible for aid funds at the academy, have been trained in this methodology, passed an exam and obtained the PRINCE2

Foundation certificate – an international certification of substantive and practical knowledge in the application of the PRINCE2 method in project management.

There is also the PRINCE2 Practitioner certificate, which is also an international certification of substantive knowledge for experienced practitioners in project management based on the PRINCE2 methodology. However, in order to obtain it, you must first pass the PRINCE2 Practitioner exam.

The entire project management cycle is described in the form of a decision of the Commandant-Rector of APol, an internal provision regulating issues related to project implementation for a specific project. Each project has a provision created for the purpose of its implementation, regulating its implementation on the premises of the university, as well as outside, in the case where APol is a project partner. The situation is similar in the Police field units (PCCs, Police Schools, KGP), where separate internal regulations are created for the purposes of project implementation.

What, then, does the use of a specific methodology for managing national security defence projects in the Police give? Can it be

Figure 2. Project management team structure based on PRINCE2 methodology

Source: A. Murray, PRINCE2™ – *Skuteczne zarządzanie projektami*, Londyn: TSO 2009, p. 36.

a cure for problems in projects? Does the use of an appropriate methodology guarantee the success of a project? A project management methodology tells you how to run a project in a controlled manner. At the same time, it does not ensure the elimination of problems that may arise during its implementation, but successively implemented it can guarantee a number of important elements, which include:

- Ø full control of the project from inception to completion;
- Ø full and appropriate involvement of all stakeholders;
- Ø guarantee of an up-to-date business case for the project and therefore security for the business funding the project,
- Ø others.

It is also important to realise that the methodology tells you what to do and why you should do it when managing a project, but says very little about how to do it. This approach, on the one hand, gives freedom to the project manager in the choice of project management tools and techniques, while on the other hand, it is difficult to treat a methodology without implementation mechanisms as a complete project management tool.

It is impossible to list and describe in a few words all aspects of project management in the Police on the basis of the PRINCE2 methodology. However, it is worth bearing in mind the predispositions of individual employees for the tasks they perform, their competences and experience. It is also important that the relationships between individual positions, both civilian and uniformed, guarantee continuity of work in the project, clear responsibilities and, most importantly, give confidence that at any time there will be someone in the project office who can take appropriate action in the event of a crisis situation. It is therefore worth remembering about an effective flow of information between the various departments, as a duplicated mistake can have severe consequences. A project coordinator should not at the same time be the only person familiar with the entire project, as his/her absence may paralyse the project

work and, although no one is irreplaceable, it is worth bearing in mind when assigning responsibilities that even the best sometimes fall ill or take a rest, and that abandoned and untimely project activities may result in drastic consequences for the entire police unit.

4. CONCLUSIONS.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that there is no ideal project management structure to fit every project. Especially in the case of projects co-financed by the European Social Fund, where the variety of positions and links between them is particularly large. It is also not useful to model the structures of similar projects carried out in other even the best institutions. After all, each organisation is governed by its own laws, has a different culture, resources or environment. So when planning how to manage projects, you need to take these factors into account. Therefore, the more time we devote to planning, the fewer surprises will await us at the project implementation stage, and thus the fewer sleepless nights in the project office and subsequent negative consequences.

The Police Headquarters provides support to the police field units, not only through the development of analyses and information materials on obtaining and use of aid funds, but also through a series of meetings with people working in units involved in obtaining aid funds and implementing in the Police. Thanks to these activities, it becomes possible to exchange knowledge and experience of units in the field in question. In addition, projects with the participation of the Police are presented, threats and barriers to their implementation are pointed out, as well as new solutions and opportunities for EU support at conferences and meetings organised by the Police Academy in Szczytno, which has extensive experience in obtaining and implementing projects using aid funds.

In conclusion, it should also be emphasised that every project will be successful if we manage to develop the right competencies related to the ability to independently and effectively manage projects (not only Europe-

an), irrespective of the constantly changing rules, guidelines and procedures of individual specific programmes [9].

Often project failure is due to poor project management, the failure to use the right management methodology. How a project is

managed largely determines its success. Proper project management is one element of the success not only of the project itself, but also of the success of the applicant and of those to whom the support, whether in kind or financial, has been directed.

BIBLIOGRAFIE

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bradley. K., Podstawy Metodyki Prince2, Centrum Rozwiązań Menadżerskich S.A., Warszawa 2005.
- Ducan W. R., A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge, Project Management Institute, For Campus Boulevard 1996.
- Jarnuszkiewicz A., Planowanie projektu decyduje o sukcesie [in:] Fundusze Europejskie nr 5/2008
- Kisielnicki J., Zarządzanie projektami. Ludzie, procedury. Warszawa 2011.
- Matoga K., Urzędnicy muszą umieć zarządzać projektami, www.samorząd.infor.pl, 24.09.2007.
- Murray A., PRINCE2™ – Skuteczne zarządzanie projektami, OGC Official Product, Publication Sourced from the Official Publisher of PRINCE2™, The Stationery Office, London 2009.
- Ministerstwo Gospodarki i Pracy, Podręcznik Zarządzania Cyklem projektu, May 2004.
- Rosiński J., Zarządzanie projektem : model najlepszych praktyk, Kraków: IFC Press, 2003.
- Stefanicka A. Zarządzanie projektem unijnym i związane z nim ryzyko [in:] Prawo Przedsiębiorcy of 10.03.2010.
- Szuszman M., Fundusze unijne od podstaw (2007–2013), przewodnik metodyczny, Włocławek 2010
- Wachowiak P., Kierowanie zespołem projektowym [in:] Zarządzanie projektem europejskim, Warszawa 2007.
- Weiss E., Bitkowska A., Samorząd terytorialny beneficjentem środków unijnych, Warszawa 2015.
- Wysocki R. K., Efektywne zarządzanie projektami, Ed. III, Wyd. Helion, 2005.
- Zajączkowska A., Koordynator projekty. Instrukcja skutecznego zarządzania projektami unijnymi z suplementem elektronicznym do monitoringu zadań, Gdańsk 2010.

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